

Performance of Chinese hybrid rice in the Philippines

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In the Philippines, hybrid rice (HR) technology is now used as a key approach for increasing rice production. In recent years, the Philippine Department of Agriculture (DA)-PhilRice strengthened its HR program through collaboration with rice research and development institutes of other countries such as China. A demonstration of Chinese HR technology in the country was implemented under a Technical Cooperation Agreement between the DA and the Ministry of Agriculture of the People's Republic of China. The objectives were to test the yield and general adaptation of elite Chinese rice hybrids in different parts of the country and to identify hybrids for possible commercial seed production and large-scale cultivation.

Thirteen Chinese hybrids were tested at eight locations during the 2000 dry season (DS), while six hybrids were tested at 19 locations (8 in Luzon, 4 in the Visayas, and 7 in Mindanao) during the 2000 wet season (WS). These were planted together with local hybrid PSBRc72H or Mestizo and the best and most popular variety in the area. The testing sites (see figure) represented major rice-growing areas in the Philippines and have favorable growing environments and good irrigation and drainage systems. The total area for each site ranged from 0.4 to 1.5 ha. Yield data were taken by using cut samples of 30 m² hybrid⁻¹ variety⁻¹.

In the DS, Mestizo yielded the highest across locations and under favorable locations (no pest and disease incidence and yields

of >4 t ha⁻¹), with an average of 7.2 and 8.9 t ha⁻¹, respectively (see table). Among the Chinese hybrids, Jin You 63 yielded the highest, with a mean of 5.7 t ha⁻¹ across locations and 7.7 t ha⁻¹ under fa-

vorable environments. During the WS, Shan You Duoqi I yielded the highest across locations and under favorable conditions (13 out of 19 locations), with a mean of 5.6 and 7.4 t ha⁻¹, respectively.

Testing sites for technology demonstration of Chinese rice hybrids, 2000, Philippines.

Under favorable environments, this hybrid outyielded Mestizo and the local check by 19% and 30%, respectively.

Overall, local hybrid Mestizo was superior to and had better adaptability than the Chinese hybrids, both under favorable environments and across environments during the DS. Some Chinese hybrids such as Jin You 63 had yields comparable with those of local inbred varieties. Although Mestizo outyielded this hybrid by more than 1 t ha⁻¹ under favorable environments, Jin You 63 matured 15 d earlier (see table). Shan You Duoxi I, another early maturing hybrid, exhibited superiority under favorable conditions and across locations during the WS; hence, these two hybrids may be preferred over Mestizo in some areas of the country with short rice-growing periods (e.g., northeastern Luzon). Seed production of these hybrids in these areas may, thus, be explored. Some Chinese hybrids such as Jin You 198, which yielded more than 11 t ha⁻¹ at one location during the DS and WS, may also be suited for specific regions of the country. Furthermore, under circumstances in which no diseases were noted, most Chinese hybrids had a notable performance.

Results, however, indicated that the potential yields of Chinese hybrids were not realized under Philippine conditions. One major reason could be the shortening of the growth duration from 122–153 d in China to only 100–114 d in the Philippines (see table). Consequently, the period between the vegetative and reproductive stages was reduced, leading to fewer tillers, fewer panicles, and consequently lower yields. Another reason was the suscepti-

Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) and average maturity (d) of Chinese rice hybrids under Philippine conditions, 2000.

Entry	Mean yield (t ha ⁻¹)				Maturity (d)		
	DS		WS		China	Philippines	
	Across locations	Favorable ^a	Across locations	Favorable ^a		DS	WS
Shan You Duoxi I	5.0	7.0	5.6	7.4	148	105	107
Shan You 46	4.8	6.6	–	–	125	103	–
Wei You 46	4.5	6.2	–	–	122	100	–
Il You 58	4.9	6.9	–	–	142	108	–
Jin You 63	5.7	7.7	4.8	6.1	139	103	106
Shi You 63	5.0	6.3	5.0	6.2	122	114	112
Yi You 96	5.3	7.1	–	–	126–130	106	–
Shan You Gui 99	4.2	6.4	–	–	125	105	–
Jin You Gui 99	4.9	7.3	–	–	122	102	–
Wei You 198	4.9	6.7	–	–	123–135	103	–
Jin You 198	5.2	7.2	5.0	6.6	123	104	104
Shan You 198	5.2	7.2	4.3	5.5	na	102	108
Il You 501	5.4	6.8	–	–	154	112	–
Pei Liang You Te Qing	–	–	4.5	5.8	na	–	108
PSBRc72H (local hybrid)	7.2	8.9	5.5	6.2	–	118	120
Local check	6.5	7.5	5.0	5.7	–	111	115

^aAv of sites unaffected by rice tungro virus; yields >4 t ha⁻¹; na = not available.

bility of Chinese hybrids to local rice diseases, such as rice tungro virus disease, that caused considerable yield losses. Hence, further improvement in resistance breeding may be required before these hybrids can be widely adapted locally. Chinese hybrids may be

grown in locations where diseases are absent or minimal.

Results indicated that the direct introduction of hybrids from other countries without prior testing may not be a sound strategy in commercializing hybrid rice technology.

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